

Positionality Statement for the EcoWeaver & TReK research network (see <https://ecoweaver.hi-knowledge.org/>)

Positionality

Acknowledging positionality recognizes the potential influence of a researcher's social position and identity on various aspects of their research. Positionality refers to an individual's worldview and the stance they take in relation to research and its context ([Holmes, 2020](#)). It encompasses beliefs about reality, knowledge, and values, which in turn influence the approach to research. These beliefs are shaped by personal experiences and various self-identifications, including national origin, geographic location, gender, ethnicity, disability status, social class, and other factors that contribute to the social position or location.

We express our positionality to provide the reader with a clear understanding of our background and identity. By being transparent, we aim to provide essential context for users of our research, acknowledging how our perspectives shape our approaches and outcomes. By offering a positionality statement, we strengthen our work through promoting transparency and reflexivity in our research.

We update our positionality statement once a year.

Positionality statement

Our team shares the scientifically backed and evidence-based perspective that we are living in a [triple planetary crisis](#) and that we want to help tackle it. We specifically focus on the issue of biodiversity loss and, more generally, on the environmental crisis. All members have a tertiary education and work within an interdisciplinary space. Collectively, we combine a variety of disciplinary backgrounds, including ecology, computer science, philosophy, education and social sciences. In the group, philosophers have adopted a practice-oriented approach with an interest in the approach of "[Philosophy in Science](#)" where the results of the philosophical investigation should be relevant to science. Team members consist of a diversity of career stages (e.g. Professors, senior and early career scientists, PhD, MSc, and BSc). As a team, we have diverse cultural backgrounds, but the majority of team members identify as being of European descent. Further, some members identify as Latin American or First Nation. Our research affiliations and fundings are mostly in the Northern hemisphere, with project instigators based in Germany and Canada (Figure 1). Most of our interactions, discussions and work outputs are in the English language.

Figure 1: Map showing the nationality of EcoWeaver team members (green shading) and locations of the institutions they are affiliated with (red dots)

Our position and funding opportunities influences our work, including the development of our ideas and outcomes. For example, our position shapes our understanding of causality as well as our understanding of which data to prioritize, methods to integrate, and processes to follow. Furthermore, the selection of problems to solve could be biased and not reflect different local issues. Similarly, the solutions proposed underestimate local contexts with a risk to being irrelevant for certain populations, communities and local situations. Moreover, our position comports the risk of overlooking certain knowledge bearers that would have been relevant to conceptualizing certain solutions. In particular, the use of the English language neglects other languages and risks overlooking different knowledge systems.

To minimize the impact of these biases, we have adopted a broad approach that is iterative and interactive. We organize regular meetings and interactive workshops with a core group who designs the process and invites participation from diverse researchers within different disciplines and from various geographical and institutional locations. We aim to create a safe space for exchange where ideas and opinions from everyone can be heard, valued and considered. This space fosters self-reflectivity within the team members to minimize propagating our biases. Furthermore, we are passionate about diversifying our community to also include people beyond academia.

Since the initiation of our collaboration, special attention has been given to collective benefit and responsibility, following core ideas of the [FAIR](#), [CLEAR](#), and [CARE principles](#). While developing the EcoWeaver infrastructure, including the Toolkit for Restoration Knowledge (TReK), our iterative and interactive approach has also led to a collection of envisioned end 'users' with heterogeneous profiles. Despite being limited by our current positionality, we aim at revising these profiles as the team expands, for example, including the perspectives of practitioners from various fields.